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Explainable AI modeling in the prediction of cardiovascular disease risk

Chara SKOUTELI ^{a,1}, Nicoletta Prenzias ^a, Antonis Kakas ^{a,b},
and Constantinos S. PATTICHIS ^{a,b}

^a*Department of Computer Science and Biomedical Engineering Research Centre,
University of Cyprus, Nicosia Cyprus*

^b*CYENS Centre of Excellence, Nicosia Cyprus*

ORCID ID: Chara Skouteli <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7243-5917>

Abstract. The objective of this study was to develop explainable AI modeling in the prediction of cardiovascular disease. The XGBoost algorithm was used followed by rule extraction and argumentation theory that provides interpretability, explainability and accuracy in scenarios with low confidence results or dilemmas. Our findings are in agreement with previous research utilizing the XGBoost machine learning algorithm for prediction of cardiovascular risk, however it is supported by rule based explainability, offering significant advantages in terms of providing both global and local explainability. Further work is needed to enhance the argumentation-based rule interpretability, explainability and accuracy in scenarios with low confidence results or dilemmas.

Keywords. Machine learning, explainability, argumentation, cardiovascular disease

1. Introduction

Although a plethora of papers have been published in the literature providing both qualitative as well as quantitative analysis of cardiovascular risk, the need still exists to incorporate in this decision-making process explainability functionality [9]. Towards this direction, this study investigates the usefulness of explainable AI modeling in the prediction of cardiovascular disease. The XGBoost algorithm was used followed by rule extraction and argumentation theory that provides interpretability, explainability and accuracy in cardiovascular disease scenarios with low confidence results or dilemmas.

We briefly review the main concepts of Explainable Machine Learning [4,5], via Argumentations, ArgEML [1,2], on which our work will be based. In the framework of ArgEML, argumentation is used both as a naturally suitable target language for Machine Learning (ML) and as a generator of explanations of the ML predictions.

ArgEML is based on acknowledging the predictive accuracy difficulties in real-life learning problems. The approach views the notion of prediction from a different perspective than that of a traditional ML model, by relaxing the requirement of accuracy and distinguishing two notions of definite prediction and ambiguity recognition. Within the ArgEML learning process we have two main operators: (1) *error reduction* and (2) *resolution of dilemmas*.

¹ Corresponding Author: Chara Skouteli, cskout01@ucy.ac.cy

2. Methodology

2.1. Data Preprocessing and Encoding

The cardiovascular dataset used in this study was obtained from Kaggle Repository (<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/sulianova/cardiovascular-disease-dataset>) and contains 70,000 samples that offer a comprehensive perspective of 11 factors contributing to cardiovascular disease. Each patient is categorized either as a high-risk instance, or low-risk otherwise. The high-risk samples consist of the 49% of the dataset and the low-risk the remaining 51%. Table 1 shows the description of each feature.

Table 1. Raw dataset features description

Feature Name	Description
ID (<i>id</i>)	Id Sampe (<i>Number</i>)
Age (<i>age</i>)	Age in days (<i>Continuous</i>)
Gender (<i>gender</i>)	Gender (0:Female, 1:Male)
Height (<i>height</i>)	Height in cm (<i>Continuous</i>)
Weight (<i>weight</i>)	Weight in kg (<i>Continuous</i>)
Systolic Blood pressure (<i>ap_hi</i>)	Systolic blood pressure in mmHg (<i>Low, Normal, Elevated, Mild, Moderate</i>)
Diastolic Blood pressure (<i>ap_lo</i>)	Diastolic blood pressure in mmHg (<i>Low, Normal, Elevated, Mild, Moderate, Severe</i>)
Cholesterol (<i>cholesterol</i>)	Cholesterol level (1: normal, 2: above normal, 3: well above normal)
Glucose level (<i>gluc</i>)	Glucose level (1: normal, 2: above normal, 3: well above normal)
Smoking (<i>smoke</i>)	Smoking (0: No Smoking, 1: Smoking)
Alcohol Intake (<i>alco</i>)	Alcohol Intake (0: Non-Alcohol, 1: Alcohol Intake)
Physical Activity (<i>active</i>)	Activity Level (0: No Activity, 1: Activity)
Cardiovascular Disease (<i>cardio</i>)	Cardiovascular disease (0: Healthy, 1: Cardiovascular Disease)

Prior to analysis, the dataset underwent extensive preprocessing to address missing values, outliers and inconsistencies. About 10,000 records with missing values and outliers were excluded. A new feature, body mass index (BMI), was calculated from the patient height and weight features, which were then removed from the dataset. To enhance the explainability and interpretability of the model, continuous variables were converted into categorical labels. The features of age, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, cholesterol and glucose levels were divided into predefined intervals chosen based on domain knowledge as documented in Table 1.

2.2. Learning Methodology

The XGBoost learning algorithm [3] was applied on the dataset. This is a gradient boosted decision tree consisting of an ensemble of weak learners. The dataset was split into learning data, consisting of 70% of data points, while the remainder was used for testing. The number of estimators was limited to 50 while the depth of each one up to 4. The selection of those metrics is important to generate less and more generic rules but still accurate.

2.3. Rule extraction Process

In this next phase we used the TE2Rules (Tree Ensemble to Rules) algorithm to extract rules from the learned model [6]. The use of this rule extraction requires that we set a

primary or positive class. In our methodology we can repeat the extraction for either label as the primary one, i.e. work with two trained models, one for the high-risk label and another one for the low-risk label in the learning phase. Each individual rule takes the form “If feature_i > t_i and feature_j ≤ t_j...and feature_k ≤ t_k, then model prediction = 1,” where the label 1 signifies the positive class, e.g. “If Cholesterol > well above normal and Systolic Blood Pressure ≤ Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure then Risk Level = High.”

The mined subset of rules can explain each model with high fidelity on positive predictions. After mining the rules for both labels (high risk and low risk) we generated a set of rules that covers both labels. Those rules will be further evaluated and prioritized using the process described as following: each extracted rule was applied to the dataset, and its accuracy over the covered data was recorded, along with the number of samples that yielded a positive result. By evaluating both the coverage and accuracy of each rule, we gained valuable insights for the effectiveness of the rule set.

3. Results

Table 2 presents the results obtained from the XGBoost model. Table 3 displays the most important rules supporting high risk, while Table 4 exhibits the rules supporting low risk. For each rule, we track its coverage within the dataset, indicating the percentage of data samples that satisfy the rule, as well as its accuracy, which represents the proportion of correctly predicted data samples that adhere to the rule. Building upon the initial assessment in the first phase, the second phase focused on selecting the minimum number of most accurate rules that together covered the whole training data set. Table 5 presents the outcomes of sequentially applying the rules in the dataset, starting with those possessing higher coverage. Finally, we calculate the *definite prediction accuracy* of the high risk predictions, meaning that we calculate the percentage of data for which a theory provides a *definite* correct prediction. Thus, there is not any other conclusion that is in conflict with the conclusion of interest [1]. The *definite prediction accuracy* calculated by removing the *dilemma* data samples from both training and testing sets and calculating the high rule set accuracy. Table 6 presents the results, as expected after removing dilemmas the performance is enhanced in both datasets.

Table 2. XGBoost model performance

Data Set	Number of Samples	Specificity	Sensitivity	Accuracy
Training Set	40,000	79.31%	65.03%	72.42%
Testing Set	20,000	79.25%	65.03%	72.32%

Table 3. Rules supporting high risk

Rule	Performance
Rule 1: Systolic Blood Pressure > Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 24.60% Accuracy: 83.82%
Rule 2: Age Group > 40-49 <u>and</u> Diastolic Blood > Hypertension Stage 1 (Mild) <u>and</u> Systolic Blood Pressure > Normal Systolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 20.64% Accuracy: 77.19%
Rule 3: Age Group > 50-59 <u>and</u> Diastolic Blood > Elevated Diastolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 12.48% Accuracy: 69.08%
Rule 4: Cholesterol > well above normal <u>and</u> Systolic Blood Pressure ≤ Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 6.50% Accuracy: 70.75%
Rule 5: Active is No <u>and</u> Age Group > 50-59 <u>and</u> Systolic Blood Pressure ≤ Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure <u>and</u> Systolic Blood Pressure > Normal Systolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 4.91% Accuracy: 79.25%

Table 4. Rules supporting low risk

Rule	Performance
Rule 1: Age Group \leq 50-59 <u>and</u> Cholesterol \leq well above normal <u>and</u> Diastolic Blood \leq Hypertension Stage 1 (Mild) <u>and</u> Systolic Blood Pressure \leq Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 50.00% Accuracy: 72.00%
Rule 2: Age Group \leq 50-59 <u>and</u> BMI Level \leq Normal <u>and</u> Diastolic Blood \leq Hypertension Stage 1 (Mild) <u>and</u> Systolic Blood Pressure \leq Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 23.48% Accuracy: 73.99%
Rule 3: Age Group \leq 40-49 <u>and</u> Cholesterol \leq well above normal <u>and</u> Systolic Blood Pressure \leq Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 21.35% Accuracy: 76.63%
Rule 4: Systolic Blood Pressure \leq Normal Systolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 17.57% Accuracy: 75.74%
Rule 5: Cholesterol \leq above normal <u>and</u> Diastolic Blood \leq Elevated Diastolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 15.80% Accuracy: 73.88%
Rule 6: Active Yes <u>and</u> Age Group \leq 50-59 <u>and</u> Age Group $>$ 40-49 <u>and</u> BMI Level \leq Normal <u>and</u> Cholesterol \leq well above normal <u>and</u> Systolic Blood Pressure \leq Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure	Covers: 11.14% Accuracy: 71.70%

Table 5. Selected rule set performance

Data Set	Number of Samples	Specificity	Sensitivity	Accuracy
Training Set	40,000	78.60%	64.99%	71.95%
Testing Set	20,000	78.61%	64.84%	71.85%

Table 6. Final performance evaluation

Data Set	Number of Samples	Dilemmas	Definite Specificity	Definite Sensitivity	Definite Accuracy
Training Set	40,000	5%	81.45%	63.45%	72.83%
Testing Set	20,000	5.1%	81.48%	63.32%	72.69%

4. Concluding Remarks and Future Work

Our findings are in agreement with previous research utilizing the XGBoost machine learning algorithm for prediction cardiovascular risk [7, 8], which demonstrates enhanced performance compared to alternative machine learning algorithms. Furthermore, upon comparing the results between the extracted rules and the XGBoost model, it is evident that the rule-based approach exhibits slightly lower overall accuracy compared to the original model. However, it offers significant advantages in terms of providing both global and local explainability. Additionally, the rule-based approach demonstrates improved performance in minimizing false negatives, a critical factor in the medical domain.

In addition to global explainability, local explainability is also provided, as demonstrated in the example below.

<p>Input: Gender: <i>female</i>, Cholesterol: <i>well above normal</i>, Glucose Level: <i>normal</i>, Smoking: <i>No</i>, Alcohol: <i>No</i>, Active: <i>No</i>, BMI Level: <i>Underweight</i>, Age Group: <i>40-49</i>, Diastolic Blood: <i>Normal Diastolic Blood Pressure</i>, Systolic Blood Pressure: <i>Normal Systolic Blood Pressure</i>.</p> <p>Prediction: <i>High Risk</i>, Reason: <i>Cholesterol > well above normal and Systolic Blood Pressure \leq Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure</i></p>

Moreover, in cases with *dilemma* the local explanation is provided as demonstrated in the example below.

Input: Gender: *female*, Cholesterol: *normal*, Glucose Level: *normal*, Smoking: *No*, Alcohol: *No*, Active: *Yes*, BMI Level: *Normal*, Age Group: *30-39*, Diastolic Blood: *Elevated Diastolic Blood Pressure*, Systolic Blood Pressure: *Stage 1 Hypertension (Mild)*

Prediction: *dilemma*

High Risk, Reason: *Systolic Blood Pressure > Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure*

Low Risk, Reason: *Cholesterol <= above normal and Diastolic Blood <= Elevated Diastolic Blood Pressure*

The prediction for this case is in dilemma: the risk could be high because of *Systolic Blood Pressure > Elevated Systolic Blood Pressure*. It could though be low because of *Cholesterol <= above normal and Diastolic Blood <= Elevated Diastolic Blood Pressure*.

Argumentation serves as a cornerstone in both Explainable AI and Human-centric AI, providing explanations of system behaviors at a sophisticated cognitive level [9]. Furthermore, by revealing the reasoning behind machine learning predictions, we enhance not only the interpretability and transparency of AI systems but also foster trust and collaboration between humans and machines. Moreover, the classification of prediction into *definite* or *dilemmas* contribute to build stronger trust between humans and machines. Moving forward, we investigated the cost associated with providing explanations of the results in relation to the accuracy of the prediction.

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